
AN OVERVIEW OF THE ROMANIAN TECH MARKET. IS AI SHAPING THE MARKETING AND TECHNOLOGY SECTORS?

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ABSTRACT

In the AI area, the technology sector has known significant developments and new products that are meant to diversify the company's economic activity, attracting new customers and better-prepared employees. AI has an impact on both marketing activities and operational efficiency within IT companies. In this fast-forward world, where the adaptability, flexibility, and resilience of companies play a key role, the implementation of AI becomes crucial for improving the quality of the services offered, for increasing customer satisfaction, but also for obtaining competitive advantages. To see how the Romanian market is selecting the AI platforms, we conducted a survey among IT professionals that are using such tools. The results have shown that important criteria are considered when it comes to engaging in a long-term relationship with an AI platform.

Keywords: AI Technologies, New Platforms, Innovation

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1. INTRODUCTION

Digitization is perceived as the use of I.T. technologies in order to save costs and improve customer experience (Verhoef et al., 2021).

The literature has provided many definitions of marketing in the digital age. For example, Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick (2019, p. 10) described digital marketing as "achieving marketing objectives through the utilization of digital media, data, and technologies."

Similarly, Bala and Verma (2018) proposed the following definition: "digital marketing is the use of technologies to support marketing activities in order to improve knowledge about customers by satisfying their needs."

The term Marketing 4.0 can be considered a synonym for digital marketing, being described as the new generation of marketing strategies that combine offline and online interactions for a seamless consumer experience (Sundararajan, Menon, & Jayakrishnan, 2022).

Kotler et al. (2021) defined Marketing 5.0 as "the use of technologies that simulate human behavior to create, communicate, deliver, and improve value in the overall customer experience." According to the authors, companies should balance human and computer intelligence and use technology to cater to all generations, thus avoiding creating silos or resentment.

The concept such as "growth hacking" is a business scaling approach and suppose a mix between marketing, information and communication technology, with an emphasis on big data, social media and artificial intelligence (Rizvanović et al., 2023). Innovation reaches new levels by using the opportunities of digital transformation.

New technologies are helping to increase the interaction between customers and the business environment. Thus, by cultivating customer trust the companies need to apply a marketing approach centered on customer needs in which data security and privacy are respected.

NFTs, as part of the blockchain, are used to build communities and loyalty programs. Artificial intelligence enables companies to run well-targeted marketing campaigns on online platforms, such as LinkedIn and Facebook. Google etc. Metaverse is already being used to improve user experience and provide original brand communication strategies.

The digital economy can be included in the scope of any economic form that directly or indirectly uses data to allocate resources and promote productivity. It includes innovative technologies such as big data, cloud computing, the Internet of Things, blockchain, Artificial Intelligence and 5G communication. Industries as, retail and manufacturing are specific representatives of using these technologies (Cho, Yun & Ko, 2023).

Digital platforms and omnichannel marketing are widely adopted. The efficiency of marketing investments will affect firms' revenues and profits. One side, companies strive to adjust their marketing strategies to maximize their profits; on the other one, the intermediary and the manufacturer have their own risks, which will influence their decision regarding the approach omnichannel adoption (Cai & Choi, 2023).

Consequently, digital marketing is becoming more and more diverse and emerging technologies applied to digital marketing activities are a catalyst for cross-dimensional organizational impact.

2. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND MARKETING STRATEGIES

Since the revolutionary debut of Chat-GPT in 2022, the understanding and application of AI have been dramatically transformed, revealing new horizons in operational efficiency and decision-making capabilities. Marketing professionals have quickly adopted this evolution, devoting themselves to harnessing AI to optimize their daily work activities. According to the insights from McKensey, by integrating AI into the daily tasks of an employee, not only will operations be simplified, but also productivity and the quality of services offered will be improved. This change signifies an essential moment in obtaining the competitive advantage and in bringing innovation and excellence, company. Artificial intelligence has become more than just a tool; it is now an essential component of a brand's identity and strategy, symbolizing innovation and customer focus.

In terms of brand and marketing strategy, AI is asserting itself as a powerful tool for creating personalized consumer experiences (Davenport, Guha & Grewal, 2021).

According to IBM, leveraging AI to analyze vast data sets in real-time enables brands to anticipate consumer needs, suggest relevant products, and communicate targeted messages that engage consumers on a deeply personal level.

This strategic integration of AI helps businesses not only meet but exceed evolving customer expectations, cultivating loyalty and driving sustainable growth (Kornienko et al., 2015).

Thus, AI can automate complex tasks and refine internal processes using sophisticated NLP techniques. This mix of creativity-enhanced efficiency and strategic depth provided by AI is redefining how companies and marketing departments interact with potential customers and adapt to new challenges by:

- Generative artificial intelligence.
- Virtual assistants for various industries.
- Sentiment and Analysis.
- Data analysis.
- voice-activated applications.
- Bilingual applications.

3. AI ADOPTION IN EUROPE

In Europe AI development is behind the market in the United States and China. Mistral, the French AI company is constantly developing, having a competitive AI solution, but still behind the giants Google or OpenAI. Regarding the rate of AI adoption among companies in the European Union, according to Eurostat, 8% of companies have used AI for operational activity. In 2023 most companies that have used AI have more than 10 employees and come from Scandinavia and Benelux. Thus, in countries such as Denmark (15.2%), Finland (15.1%) and Luxembourg (14.4%) the percentage associated with the use of AI is higher. The lowest adoption rate was recorded in Romania (1.5%), Bulgaria (3.6%) and Hungary (3.7%).

According to SEMrush 2024 data, globally in 2023, the adoption of AI among departments and by marketing professionals was:

- 77% of marketers believe that marketing automation is critical to customer acquisition and retention.
- 88% of marketers say that the use of automation and artificial intelligence is necessary to meet customer expectations, reduce costs and remain competitive.
- Most marketers use AI to write content.

4. RESEARCH ON AI USAGE BY THE IT PROFESSIONALS

Methodology

It was conducted a survey among 300 respondents, from Romania in order to identify what are the criteria Romanians specialties consider when choosing a specific AI platform, according to their professional needs. In the survey, the respondents were asked questions that helped in contouring their usage behavior in the case of AI technologies. Another objective was to identify which are the most important competencies considered in the AI area.

The criteria used in the selection phase were the education skills focused on understanding AI and its impact.

Findings and Discussion

The most frequently used applications are virtual assistants (25% daily, 20% 2-3 times a week and 14% once a week) and personalized recommendation engines (17% daily, 13% 2-3 times a week and 11% once a week).

Frequency and types of use of AI applications

Respondents highlight that data analysis and interpretation skills will become more valuable in the age of Artificial Intelligence (37% important and 34% very important), as well as creative thinking (36% important and 33% very important).

Most important competencies considered as an added values in the AI era

The distribution is Gaussian, but it tends towards the idea that AI will indeed lead to increased competition among employees (30% tend to say it will, and 13% say it will definitely lead to competition).

Concluding Remarks

AI is an emerging technology trend when it comes to employees's usage and challenges nowadays. The most important two criteria when it comes to AI platforms are chatbots and recommendation engines.

Employees in IT appear to be results-oriented and willing to use artificial intelligence. They also value considerations such as the impact on jobs. Focusing on efficiency and how employees can have a competitive advantage in the market is another important aspect of research.

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